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EMERGENCE OF COMMUNITIES IN CENTRAL ASIA AND STAGES OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: Author explores the historical progression of community formation in Central Asia, analyzing key stages of development. His research highlights socio-economic, cultural, and political factors influencing community evolution, offering valuable insights into the region's complex history and social dynamics. This article contributes to a deeper understanding of Central Asia's societal structures and historical transformations, drawing on extensive scholarly research to illuminate pivotal stages in community development.

Keywords: Central Asia, Anau, Monjukli depe, Ovadan depe, Gavich depe, Chagmogli depe, Dashlidepe, Mullali depe, Geoksur, archeological sites, excavations.

Introduction. Central Asia is considered a unique historical-geographical and historical-cultural region. Civilization has been progressing in these regions for many centuries thanks to two large rivers - Amudarya and Syrdarya. The states that emerged in this area were distinguished by their own characteristics in ancient times and in the Middle Ages. [1,2] In ancient times, the ethnic, material culture, language, and writing of Khorezm, Sogd, and Bactrian regions were close to each other. This situation is explained by the historical-cultural forms and level of cultural development of each region.

Results. Archaeological materials serve as the main source in studying the history of these communities, in researching the processes of the emergence of the first cities and states. The issue of the emergence and development of communities is well studied in the case of the Ancient East. In this matter, A.I. The researches of Tyumenov and I.M.Dyakov in the study of Sumerian communities can be highlighted. N.B.Yankovskaya, Ugarit and Phenicia M.L.Geltser, Palestine I.D.Amusina, in ancient Elam Y.B.Yusifov, in Babylon G.Kh. Sarkisyan, in Iran M.M. D'yakov, there are studies of a number of Chinese scholars on Chinese communities. [3] Researchers such as G. M. Bongard-Levin and G. F.

Il'in studied Indian communities on the basis of written sources, while T. Jacobson's research was devoted to issues of community management.

The analysis of the above-mentioned literature shows that the development of communities in the centers of culture of the Ancient East, although they are not exactly similar to each other, developed in parallel. [4]

Group marriage (the procedure of relations between men of one clan and women of another clan) is dominant in the oldest tribal community stage. In the conditions of Central Asia, the Kaltaminor culture community of the Neolithic period can be included in this stage. At this stage, economic life is based on an exploitative economy. The property was social in nature. Seed communities live in large thatched huts. At the end of this stage, family buds begin to appear gradually on the initiative of women (Djonbaskala). [5,6]

In a community based on blood and kinship, all products were considered common property, and mutual support played a leading role. This way of life of the community does not lead to the emergence of division of labor among them. Equal distribution of products among team members does not allow further development of the team. [7]

The family community is separated from the clan community and is a free economic operator. But this team cannot live on its own. At this stage, the mother retains her position in the community. Property will still be social in nature. These include the Neolithic and Eneolithic periods in the agricultural regions of Central Asia in terms of period. During this period, women connect their fate with one of the men from another clan. Nevertheless, the influence of the uncle was still high in front of the children compared to the father. Within the mother's clan, the family begins to form, that is, women demand that their children, and the father of their children, engage in useful work for the community of their clan. As a result, the rules of group marriage are disintegrated, and family huts are formed on the initiative of women. [8,9] As observed in many ethnographic sources, (men start living in a female community) marriage arrangement is created. However, the bridegroom cannot be an equal member of the female community.

Clan communities based on blood-kinship have been well studied on the example of monuments of the Neolithic and Eneolithic period in the territory of Southern Turkmenistan. [10] It is observed that 8-10 families lived together in monuments such as Jaytun of the Neolithic period, Anau, Monjukli depe, Ovadan depe, Gavich depe, Chagmogli depe, Dashlidje depe, Mullali depe, Geoksur I of the middle Eneolithic period. In these families, furnaces, storehouses and prayer rooms were common.

Patriarchal family community (large family, neighborhood community). In our imagination, the period of Nomozgoh IV reminds us of the transition to such a historical process, while in the period of Nomozgoh V, the separation of matriarchate communities and patriarchate family communities takes place. Thus, the patriarchal family community, which is considered the third stage of the seed community, is formed. [11] This process is very active at the end of Nomozgoh V and during Nomozgoh VI. As a result, not only the Murgob Valley of Central Asia, but also the lands of South and North Bactria were appropriated, and ancient farming cultures such as Dashtli and Sopolli were formed. Local hearths of Marghiyona and Bactria belonging to the Bronze Age of the Ancient Eastern civilization were found. Now, instead of collective property, private property, patriarchal family property appeared. The family community developed and in turn became a large patriarchal family. According to our imagination, if the period of Nomozgoh IV reminds the process of the formation of a patriarchal family, then during the period of Nomozgoh V, Dashtli and Sopolli, the development of a large patriarchal family community can be observed. [12,13]

It is known that production does not always produce surplus. In this case, the enrichment or impoverishment of a family group is observed, not an individual. As a result, poor families become financially dependent on rich families. [14] The "father" of the poor family did not participate in the management of the patriarchal family community, but the heads of the rich families participated. As the division of labor increases, so does the tendency to own private property among the patriarchal family community. [15]

The inhabitants of Sopollitepa developed all kinds of handicrafts (pottery, fine art-jewelry, bronze objects), house building, military work, agriculture. For this, they used all the internal possibilities. According to archaeologist scientist Sh. Shaydullaev, there were three ways to further develop the community:

1. expansion of the territory of the community due to the development of new lands;
2. trade development;
3. conquering and robbing neighboring nations.

The people of Sopollitepa chose the first way. A.A. Askarov connects the issue of the crisis of Sopollitepa with the migration of the population to a new place, to the territory of Djarkutan.

So, the stages of emergence and development of communities in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, developed in parallel with the communities of the Ancient East. The development of communities may not be consistent across regions, but communities in all regions of the Ancient Near East passed through the stages analyzed above. [16]

Conclusion. The collectives consisted of the production economy that arose at the end of the primitive collective system, and had their own management methods. Organization of production, maintenance of order and peace of community members, communication with neighboring communities formed the basis of community life.

Community management methods, especially rural community management, cannot be standardized. In this case, it is necessary to focus on what the production method of this village is based on. It is necessary to take into account the religious unity that binds the members of the community and the role of religious representatives or another layer - the military (group of armed men) in the community.

The development of communities shows that the first state symbols appeared at different stages. The improvement of the management method in the primitive community land, the development of trade and commodity exchange methods increased the need for statehood of the community union.

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